

Poster

XylAppEU_2.1.3 for precise acquisition and traceability of monitoring data of *Xylella fastidiosa* in the EU

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Abstract: XylAppEU 2.1.3 will be launched at the end of 2019 as the final version of the Android application XylApp_1.2.4 used for the official monitoring of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Apulia, Italy. It was developed on the basis of the characteristics and input received from stakeholders in three EU pilot areas (Córdoba, Spain; Crete, Greece; Apulia, Italy) and from other project partners. A video tutorial of the previous version (2.1.2) was prepared and launched on the project website and the application download was available for testing between partners. This version considers the following aspects which will be implemented with additional input from partners after testing: (i) analysis of the scenario in the specific country; (ii) identification of the specific needs and resolution conditions in relation to the different users; (iii) definition of the featured applications, constraints, performance, interfaces and any other features to fulfil users' needs; (iv) active engagement of end-users for the finalisation and validation of the app.

The advanced application XylAppEU_2.1.3 was equipped with grids of different sizes (e.g. 100 m x 100 m, 1 km x 1 km) of the three pilot sites, based on the free formats available from the European Environment Agency. With regard to the hardware and other minor functions, different parameters (sensor configuration, connectivity and size of the display) were implemented for the most popular platforms (e.g. Google Android). The following specific features were also implemented: transmission protocols for data sending over the internet; inclusion of grid visualisation of the pilot sites for sample localisation at EU level (ETRS89-LAEA Europe); development of a GIS model for management of EU cartographic data. A new graphic interface has been made, user friendly, which guarantees better functionality and integration of modules, beside guidelines or better management by users. This version allows the acquisition, storage and transmission of data in different formats. As for the previous version, a video tutorial on XylAppEU_2.1.3 will be prepared for dissemination purposes.